

Physicochemical and biological studies on Co^{II}-ascorbic acid complex

Ratnesh Das and K. S. Pitre*

Department of Chemistry, Dr. H. S. Gour University, Sagar-470 003, Madhya Pradesh, India

E-mail : ratnesh_das@rediffmail.com

Manuscript received 7 September 2004, revised 10 May 2005, accepted 30 December 2005

Abstract : Physicochemical and microbial studies on Co^{II}-ascorbic acid complex have been done in solid and aqueous phase. On the basis of elemental analysis, polarographic studies and amperometric titrations, the metal : drug ratio has been worked out to be 1 : 1. IR spectral studies have been used to ascertain metal : ligand binding site. Microbial studies on the complex was done against various pathogenic bacteria viz. *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella typhi*, *Vibrio cholerae* and *Diplococcus pneumoniae*. The results of the microbial studies with the metal : drug complex revealed that the drug : metal complex is more potent against the pathogenic bacteria as compared to the pure drug, ascorbic acid.

Keywords : Cobalt(II) complex, ascorbic acid, biological studies.

It has been recently shown¹ that ascorbic acid suppresses the production of HIV in a latently infected T-lymphocytic cell line. Ascorbic acid can protect from oxidative damage to DNA and lipids that may lead to aging, cancer and other dys functions like AIDS². In continuation of our work on the study of electrochemical, bio-inorganic, microbial and pharmacological behaviour of some metal-drug complexes³, the present paper deals with the said studies on the Co^{II}-ascorbic acid (anti-AIDS drug) complex.

Experimental

Material and methods :

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR/B.D.H. grade. The ascorbic acid was procured from Sigma Chemical Company, USA. Double-distilled water was used as solvent. Polarographic measurements were made on an Elico (India) DC-Polarograph model no. 357. The electrode system consisted of a Dropping Mercury Electrode (DME) as a working electrode, a coiled platinum wire as an auxiliary electrode and saturated calomel electrode (SCE) as reference electrode.

The amperometric titration was performed on a manually operated setup comprising of a polyflex galvanometer (sensitivity 8.1×10^{-9} amp/div.) and an AJCO Varnier Potentiometer. A DME was used as an indicator electrode and a calomel electrode served as reference electrode. The capillary characteristics of the DME had a $m^{2/3}$, $t^{1/6} = 2.13$ mg^{2/3}, s^{1/2} at 50 cm effective height of the mercury column. The pH of the test solutions was measured on an Elico dig-

ital pH meter Model LI-108. The elemental i.e. C and H analysis of the complex was done on a Heraeus Varlo Erba elemental analyser model-1108. The IR spectrum of the solid complex was recorded using KBr pellets on a Perkin-Elmer-IR Spectrophotometer, model-379.

Table 1. Principal IR signals (cm⁻¹) and their assignments for ascorbic acid and its Co^{II}-complex

Assignments	Ascorbic acid	Co ^{II} -complex
Free -OH stretching vibration	3525	3525
C-H stretching vibration	3020	3020
>C=O stretching vibration	1754	1754
C=C stretching vibration	1674	1674
Secondary -OH stretching vibration	1320	1320
Primary -OH stretching vibration	1000	920

General procedure for polarographic and amperometric titration :

Experimental sets were prepared by keeping overall cobalt (metal ion) and potassium chloride (supporting electrolyte) concentration fixed at 1.0 M respectively. The ligand concentration was varied from 0.0 mM to 16 mM. The pH of the test solution was adjusted to 6.0 ± 0.1 using, HCl/NaOH solution. Experimental sets, each having different but known amount of the drug under study were prepared in appropriate quantity of supporting electrolyte (potassium chloride) at pH = 6.0 ± 0.1 and titrated separately against the standard solution of the titled Co^{II} ions whose pH has been adjusted to that of the titrate (6.0 ± 0.1).

Synthesis procedure of the solid complex : Cobalt nitrate and ascorbic acid (drug) solution were separately prepared

in distilled water and were mixed in 1 : 1 molar ratio, the mixture was then refluxed in a round bottom flask for 1–2 h. The residue (complex) was filtered and washed thoroughly to remove any unreacted materials. The complex was dried at 40 °C and stored over P₄H₁₀. Elemental analysis was carried out for C, H and cobalt (gravimetry)⁴. The IR spectrum of the solid complex was recorded using KBr pellets.

Antibacterial studies : Rapers⁵ paper disc method was followed for the microbial screening of Co^{II}-ascorbic acid complex against various bacteria viz. *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella typhi*, *Vibrio cholerae* and *Diplococcus pneumoniae*. The antimicrobial activities were recorded by measuring the inhibition zone against complex under study. Similar experiment was repeated with the control drug (ascorbic acid).

The number of replicates in each case were three, percentage inhibition was calculated using the following formula.

$$\% \text{ Inhibition} = A - B/A \times 100$$

where *A* represents the diameter of the inhibition zone for control (ascorbic acid) and *B* represents the diameter of the inhibition zone for sample (Co^{II}-ascorbic acid complex).

Results and discussion

Polarographic measurements :

Polarographic behaviour of ascorbic acid with Co^{II} and its complex with the ligand under study were found to be reversibly reduced involving two electrons which was evidenced from the plots of log plot slopes. The reduction was found to be diffusion controlled, which was evidenced by the plot of *i*_d vs \sqrt{h} corr.

On gradual increase of the ascorbic acid concentration the half wave potential of Co^{II} shifted to more negative value and the diffusion current shortened thereby showing complex formation between Co^{II} with ascorbic acid. To study the composition and formation constant of the complex, plot of $\Delta E_{1/2}$ (shift in *E*_{1/2}) i.e. (*E*_{1/2})_c – (*E*_{1/2})_s against log *C*_x (logarithm of the concentration of the ligand) was drawn. The plot is linear showing the formation of single complex species in solution. Lingane's treatment of the observed polarographic data reveals 1 : 1 metal : ascorbic acid complex formation with log β₁ = 5.29.

Amperometric determination of ascorbic acid with Co^{II} : Co^{II} gives a well defined polarographic wave in 1.0 *M* KCl at pH = 6.0 ± 0.1. The diffusion current was found to be proportional to the concentration of Co^{II}. The ascorbic acid drug does not produce a wave under the said experimental conditions. The plateau potential for the polarographic

wave of Co^{II} (–1.2 V) vs Hg pool was applied for carrying out amperometric titrations. On performing the amperometric titration of drug solution with standard solution of Co^{II}, the current volume plots resulted in L-shaped curves. The end point as located by graphical method revealed metal to the drug ratio of 1 : 1, which is in agreement with the author's observations on the metal : ligand equilibria using polarographic method.

IR spectra : The structurally important frequencies of IR bands for ascorbic acid and its complex with Co^{II} have been tabulated in Table 1. A comparison of the IR data for the drug and its Co^{II} complex reveals that the band at 1000 cm^{–1} in the spectrum of the drug is shifted to 920 cm^{–1} in the spectrum of the complex, indicating the involvement of primary –OH of the drug in the complex formation.

Antibacterial study : Antibacterial activity of its compounds (0.01 *M*) was evaluated by paper disc method against *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella typhi*, *Vibrio cholerae* and *Diplococcus pneumoniae*. The complex showed enhanced activity against all the test pathogen except for *Vibrio cholerae*. The percentage inhibition over control drug are –41.6, –31.1 and –57.1 against *E. coli*, *S. typhi* and *D. pneumoniae* respectively. Hence, the complex is found to be more toxic as compared to the control drug against the test bacteria.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the Head, Department of Chemistry, Dr. H. S. Gour University, Sagar for providing necessary laboratory facilities.

References

1. S. Harakeh and R. J. Jariwalla, *Nutrition*, 1995, **11**, 684.
2. E. Eylar, I. Baez, J. Navas and C. Mercado, *J. Health Sci.*, 1996, **15**, 21; R. F. Cathcart, *Med. Hypothesis*, 1984, **14**, 423; S. Harakeh, R. J. Jariwalla and L. Pauling, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA*, 1990, **87**, 7245; A. Favier, C. Sappey, P. Leclerc, P. Faure and M. Micoud, *Chem Biol. Interact.*, 1994, **91**, 165.
3. S. Narad, N. N. Mishra, P. Pandey, A. Kumar and K. S. Pitre, *Indian J. Physicol. Pharmacol.*, 1995, **39**, 166; *Z. Analiticheskoj*, 1996, **51**, 63; A. V. Trivedi and K. S. Pitre, *Vigyan Parishad and Anusandhan Patrika, Allahabad*, 1989, **32**, 41; *J. Electrochem. Soc. (India)*, 1988, **37**, 273.
4. I. Bassett, R. C. Renny, G. H. Jeffery and J. Mendam, "Vogel's Text Book of Quantitative Analysis", ELBS, London, 4th ed., 1978, 440.
5. Y. H. Loo, P. S. Skell, H. H. Thurnberry, J. Ehrlich, J. M. Megwer, G. M. Savage and J. C. Sylvester, *J. Bacteriol.*, 1945, **50**, 701; K. B. Raper, D. E. Alexander and K. Coghi, *J. Bacteriol.*, 1944, **48**, 693.